

WAYS OF DEVELOPING CREATIVE ABILITIES OF STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract: the process of developing the creativity of future bachelors of pedagogical education requires scientific justification and methodological support due to insufficient cognitive, theoretical and practical significance. That's why we tried to present our article on this topic. We can learn how to develop the creativity of future students.

Keyword: knowledge, skills, skills, creativity, pedagogical orientation, creativity, divergence, competence

Annotatsiya: Bo'lajak pedagogik ta'lim bakalavriatlarining kreativligini rivojlantirish jarayoni yetarli bilim, nazariy va amaliy ahamiyatga ega bo'lmaganligi sababli ilmiy asoslash va uslubiy ta'minlashni talab qiladi. Shuning uchun ham shu maqolamizni shu mavzuda bayon etishga harakat qildik. Bo'lajak talabalarning kreativligini qanday rivojlantirish kerakligini bilib olishimiz mumkin.

Kalit so'z: bilim, ko'nikma, malaka, kreativlig, pedagogik yo'nalish, Ijodkorlik, divergent, kompetensiya

Аннотация: процесс развития креативности будущих бакалавров педагогического образования требует научного обоснования и методического обеспечения ввиду недостаточной познавательной, теоретической и практической значимости. Вот почему мы постарались изложить нашу статью на эту тему. Мы можем узнать, как развивать креативность будущих студентов.

Ключевое слово: знания, умения, навыки, креативность, педагогическая направленность, креативность, дивергентность, компетентность

Summarizing the definitions of creativity of foreign scientists, we can conclude that there is no single approach to this problem, but the definitions presented to us can be classified according to four aspects that consider creativity: the creative process, the creative product, the creative personality and the creative environment (the sphere, structure, social context that forms the requirements for the product of creativity). By joining the creative process, the individual is activated in a creative environment, acquires creative personality traits, and then actualizes in a creative product.

Creative process. Most foreign scientists who consider creativity to be a process (E.P.Torrens, S.Mednik, H.E.Trick) agree that creativity is divided into 3 actions:

- action to advance the hypothesis;
- the act of creativity;
- the action of a logically developed idea.

Many further studies have been directed to detail these actions while maintaining the basis of the theory.

According to the research of Poincaré and Hadamard, the creative process is carried out in 4 stages:

- the preparatory stage involves an attempt to solve the problem in the usual way;
- the incubation period consists in realizing that the usual methods of solving the problem do not work, in this regard, its solution is postponed, the person goes to another activity.
- the concept is characterized by the sudden appearance of a response from the unconscious;
- verification involves a comprehensive analysis of the suitability and permissibility of the found solution

A.M. Scientists from the Matyushkin Scientific School presented the following interpretation of the stages of creative activity:

- active main activity;
- understanding contradiction;
- the need to find answers;
- self-expression and self-realization;
- statement.

In our opinion, the missing stage in this sequence is the reflection of the result obtained, that is, the self-assessment of the compliance of the quality of a particular product with the original concept, reaction and assessment of the quality of the product. Others are also important to identify opportunities for further improvement of the product and its activities.

Unlike logical thinking, which works with concepts, creativity, considered as a process, acts with images in order to change them, as a result of which something is created, deliberately new, previously non-existent product, object. That is, creativity is the reflection of wakefulness in unexpected, new, unusual connections and combinations. Creativity is activated when a problematic situation arises, characterized by the absence of the necessary completeness of knowledge, and when it is impossible to resolve this conflict in a logical way. The formation of a new image occurs with the help of the subject's knowledge. This requires the selection, evaluation, generalization of new images.

Creative product. The results of creativity are presented in a wide range: they can be scientific discoveries that change the direction of history, economics, as well as various masterpieces, as a result of which new directions are created in art. Such creative products are a feature of great or historical creativity and are valuable to society as a whole. Products of small or personal creativity can be an everyday solution to everyday tasks in an unusual way: updating the interior, creating original bouquets, paintings.

The creative product is primarily associated with the professional activity of a person: in literature it is an artistic text, in design activities - layouts, drawings, business cards, booklets, graphic projects and models, in educational activities - these are creative students and students.

Torrance, K. Based on Taylor's concept, he described creative product levels and described them with levels of effective creativity, invention, innovation, and creativity.

P.Jackson and S.Messik defined the following criteria for a creative product and emphasized the need for a holistic procedure for its description:

- 1) originality (statistical rarity);
- 2) meaningfulness (for example, a unique way to use an element is not always creative);
- 3) transformation (the degree of rotation of the source material is the basis for eliminating traditional restrictions);
- 4) unification (the formation of unity and harmony of elements of experience, which allows you to express a new thought in a concentrated form).

Dividing the products of creative activity into those of social and personal importance M. Proposed by Boden and associated with the difficulty of evaluating the results of creativity. In addition, M.Boden believes that it should be taken into account that a person often creates not for public recognition, but in order to experience a state of exaltation that allows him to feel like a creative person. That is why the development of the creativity of students of higher education remains one of the urgent issues.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Адолф, В.А. Мутахассиснинг малакасини оширишнинг ўқув жараёнини компетенцияга асосланган ёндашув асосида лойиҳалаш. // В.А. Адолф, И.Ю.Степанова / Россияда олий таълим. Но 3. 2008. С. 158-161.
2. М.Н Quvvatova, Sh. Alisherova Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning nutqini o'zlashtirishda lug'at ishining ahamiyati - Eurasian Journal of Academic , 2022 - in-academy.uz [1]

3. Mohira Kuvvatova “Development of students' creativity as a psychological and pedagogical problem” web of scientist: international scientific research journal 10.10.2022 [2]
4. Адолф, В.А. Мактаб-университет-корхона мажмуасида касб-ҳунар таълими тизимини лойиҳалаш. // В.А. Адолф, И.А. Ковалевич, Н.П. Чурляева / Қозон психологик-педагогик журнали. - Но 4. - 2011. - С. 77-87.
5. X Nuritdinova “maktabgacha tayyorlov yoshdagi bolalarni maktab ta'limiga tayyorlashning pedagogik va psixologik asoslari”- Eurasian Journal of Academic Research, 2022 - in-academy.uz [4]

